

FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR NON-PERFORMING LOANS IN THE ANCHOR BORROWERS PROGRAMME IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The current study examines the determinants of non-performing loans (NPLs) under the Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABP) in Nigeria. While much has been written about access to credit and loan repayment challenges faced by farmers in developing countries, little is known about the multifaceted factors responsible for NPLs of government-sponsored agricultural financing programs such as ABP. The study uses survey research design to elicit information from 162 Development Finance Officers covering the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria. The study adopted Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) for the analysis. The findings reveal that beneficiary-related factors including loan diversion, willful default, and lack of integrity exert significant influence on NPLs in the ABP. Additionally, agricultural-related factors (such as production risks, natural disasters, and poor commodity value chains) and socio-economic factors (such as corruption, culture, and household spending patterns) also significantly contribute to NPLs in the ABP. Moreover, institutional weaknesses, particularly the policy inconsistencies and lack of adequate infrastructure and security, are another systemic source of NPLs in the programme. The study concludes that for the improvement in the performance of Agricultural financing programmes, there is need to address the issues of information asymmetries, institutional weaknesses and systemic risks. The study therefore, recommends among others that a robust screening processes that assess borrowers' integrity, financial capacity, and history of loan performance should be implemented. Also, regular monitoring of loan utilization should also be instituted, leveraging digital tools to ensure compliance.

Keywords: Non-Performing Loans (NPLs), Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABP), Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

JEL Codes: G21, Q14, Q18.

1. INTRODUCTION

Non-performing loans (NPLs) represent one of the most critical challenges confronting financial institutions, particularly development finance institutions engaged in directed credit programmes. The accumulation of NPLs erodes the capacity of lenders to extend new credit, inflates intermediation costs, and ultimately threatens programme viability and institutional sustainability (Naili & Lahrchi, 2022). From a theoretical standpoint, the root causes of NPLs are widely attributed to information asymmetry, moral hazard, and weak contract enforcement mechanisms (Berger & DeYoung, 1997). Under conditions of asymmetric information,

financial institutions face the twin problems of adverse selection, whereby borrowers with the highest default risk are often most likely to seek credit and moral hazard, whereby borrowers, once funded, may engage in behaviour inconsistent with lender interests (Ozili, 2019). These are especially pronounced in agriculture finance, given the exposure to weather shocks, commodity price volatility and poorly developed value chains (Owusu et al., 2024). Comparative cross-country evidence confirms that macroeconomic deterioration, including GDP contractions, interest rate increases, and unemployment shocks, is strongly associated with rising NPLs, with the effect being more pronounced in sectors exposed to systemic risks such as agriculture (Msomi, 2022; Akinlo & Emmanuel, 2014).

The agricultural sector is vital to the Nigerian economy because it significantly contributes to food security, employment creation, and poverty alleviation (World Bank, 2020; National Bureau of Statistics, 2021). However, smallholder farmers, who constitute the dominant segment of Nigeria's agricultural workforce, face acute structural barriers to formal credit access, including the absence of acceptable collateral, low financial literacy, and geographic remoteness from formal financial institutions (Obih & Baiyegunhi, 2018; Okpukpara, 2022). Also, empirical evidence indicates that over the years, formal financial institutions are often reluctant to extend credit facilities to smallholder farmers, largely due to the sector's history of poor loan repayment performance (Balana, & Oyeyemi, 2022). Specifically, commercial bank lending to Nigeria's agricultural sector has remained substantially below the African average, reflecting deep-seated structural barriers to agricultural finance (Okpukpara, 2022; Ozioko, & Enya, 2021). This has negatively affected the country's agricultural development as limited access to credit facilities continues to constrain productivity and growth. These financing gaps have suppressed agricultural productivity and constrained rural economic transformation over successive decades.

Recognizing these challenges, the government established the Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABP) in 2015 to connect smallholder farmers to agro-processing enterprises (the anchor companies), while providing in-kind input support and credit facilities to participating farmers at concessionary interest rates (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2015). The ABP was intended to address the dual objectives of improving smallholder farmers' access to institutional finance and enhancing domestic food production by reducing dependence on food imports. However, as of February 2023, only about 52 per cent of total ABP disbursements had been repaid, with N183.53 billion deemed lost by the Central Bank of Nigeria (Nairametrics, 2024), raising critical questions about the programme's sustainability (Ogundipe & Akintola, 2020; Premium Times, 2023).

Existing studies on agricultural financing in Nigeria have focused on the general issues of credit access, funding gap and loan repayment challenges (Obih & Baiyegunhi, 2018; Owusu et al., 2024; Onyenekwe et al., 2025). However, there is limited empirical research on the determinants of NPLs in the ABP despite its status as Nigeria's flagship agricultural financing programme. The lack of empirical analysis on loan default dynamics in the intervention programmes creates a theoretical gap because the default dynamics may differ from the general banking system for various reasons (e.g. programme design, political economy etc.). The problem is also systemic because failure to address loan defaults undermines financial institutions' capacity and willingness to support initiatives targeted at improving food security and rural development (Akihir, Effiong & Adekoya, 2021).

Against this backdrop, the current study investigates the determinants of non-performing loans under the Anchor Borrowers' Programme in Nigeria. The study develops and empirically tests

a multi-dimensional framework that categorises the determinants of ABP loan default into five broad clusters which are beneficiary-related factors, agricultural and production-related factors, socio-economic factors, institutional environmental factors and programme design factors. In doing so, the study makes a twofold contribution to the literature. First, it advances knowledge on agricultural credit risk by providing empirical evidence on the specific default drivers within a directed intervention programme in a major African economy. Second, it connects the NPL problem in the ABP to the broader theoretical literature on information asymmetry, institutional weaknesses, and systemic risks in agricultural finance (Berger & DeYoung, 1997; Ozili, 2019), thereby enriching both the theoretical and policy discourse on agricultural lending in emerging economies.

Following the introduction, the rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a review of the relevant literature. Section 3 outlines the dataset and econometric methodology employed in this research. Section 4 presents the empirical findings, while Section 5 concludes with policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews Non-Performing Loans (NPLs), their contributing factors, and the theoretical framework for understanding their dynamics in the Anchor Borrowers Programme (ABP), alongside relevant empirical studies.

2.1 Conceptual Clarifications

Non-performing loans refer to credit facilities in default or close to default due to the borrower's failure to meet scheduled repayment obligations. A loan is generally classified as non-performing when principal or interest payments remain overdue for 90 days or more, or when the lender judges that full repayment is unlikely (Ehiedu & Brume-Ezewu, 2022). NPLs therefore represent impaired assets that signal heightened credit risk and weakened loan portfolio quality.

Beneficiary-related factors denote borrower-specific characteristics and behaviors that undermine repayment capacity. Among smallholder farmers, these include low financial literacy, weak fund management, limited farming experience, and unwillingness to repay. Such factors stem from personal attributes and socio-economic conditions that constrain effective loan utilization and debt servicing (Balana & Oyeyemi, 2022; Ojiako et al., 2015).

Programme-specific factors refer to structural and administrative weaknesses within the design and implementation of credit schemes that elevate default risk. In the context of the Anchor Borrowers' Programme, these include delayed disbursement, inadequate credit appraisal, weak monitoring mechanisms, and inefficient risk management systems (Umeh & Adejo, 2019). Such deficiencies compromise programme effectiveness and repayment performance.

Agricultural-related factors encompass sector-specific risks that adversely affect farm productivity and income, thereby limiting repayment capacity. These include climate variability, natural disasters, pest infestations, low yields, and weak agricultural value chains. Given Nigeria's heavy reliance on rain-fed agriculture, exposure to weather uncertainty significantly amplifies production and credit risks (Hamidan, 2019; Baba, 2023; Prince et al., 2023).

Socio-economic factors capture broader economic and social constraints that weaken farmers' financial stability. Corruption in loan administration, cultural attitudes toward credit, household expenditure pressures, inflation, and exchange rate volatility increase financial

strain and reduce repayment capacity (Gashayie & Singh, 2015). These dynamics interact with farm-level vulnerabilities to heighten default probability.

Institutional environment factors refer to weaknesses in governance, regulatory frameworks, and infrastructure that indirectly contribute to NPL occurrence. Policy inconsistency, insecurity, inadequate oversight, poor infrastructure, and limited implementing agency support constrain effective credit administration and monitoring. Such systemic inefficiencies increase the likelihood of fund misallocation and repayment failure (Nguyen, 2014; Nwonye et al., 2023).

Figure 1

Source; Authors’ Conceptualization, (2025)

This conceptual framework treats Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) in the Anchor Borrowers Programme (ABP) as a multi-dimensional failure of character, process, and environment. Grounded in Information Asymmetry Theory, the model explains how the knowledge gap between lenders and borrowers leads to adverse selection during recruitment and moral hazard post-disbursement (Stiglitz & Weiss, 1981). These theoretical failings manifest through five key determinants: Internal Drivers (H₁ & H₂): Beneficiary-related factors, such as willful default and loan diversion, suggest that borrower character is a primary predictor of default (Balana & Oyeyemi, 2022). This is often compounded by programme-specific inefficiencies, where delayed disbursements and weak monitoring regimes disrupt the agricultural calendar, forcing farmers to divert funds toward immediate consumption (Ojiako et al., 2015).

External Pressures (H₃, H₄ & H₅): Agricultural-related factors like climate shocks and pest infestations create systemic risks that make repayment physically impossible (Ejiogu, 2021). These risks are further intensified by socio-economic pressures like inflation and the cultural perception of government credit as a "political grant," as well as institutional environment factors such as regional insecurity and policy inconsistency (Nwonye et al., 2023).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Information Asymmetry Theory, originally advanced by Akerlof (1970) in his seminal analysis of the “market for lemons.” The theory explains how unequal access to information between transacting parties leads to inefficient market outcomes (Mishkin, 2019). Information Asymmetry Theory is primarily characterised by two key components: adverse selection and moral hazard. Adverse selection occurs before loan disbursement, when lenders are unable to effectively distinguish between low-risk and high-

risk borrowers due to inadequate information (Akerlof, 1970; Stiglitz & Weiss, 1981). Also, moral hazard arises after loan disbursement, when borrowers change their behavior in ways that increase default risk because monitoring and enforcement mechanisms are weak (Holmström, 1979; Mishkin, 2019). In the ABP, moral hazard is reflected in practices such as diversion of loan funds to non-agricultural uses, reduced effort in farm management, deliberate default, and prioritization of household consumption over loan repayment.

Information Asymmetry Theory provides a robust explanatory framework for the persistence of NPLs under the ABP by highlighting how imperfect information at both the pre-loan and post-loan stages undermines effective credit allocation, monitoring, and repayment. The interaction of beneficiary-related, programme-specific, agricultural, socio-economic, and institutional factors represents distinct channels through which adverse selection and moral hazard jointly influence loan performance within the programme. The theory further implies that reducing NPLs under the ABP requires institutional mechanisms that minimize information gaps, including improved beneficiary screening, stronger monitoring and evaluation systems, enhanced transparency, effective extension services, and sustained borrower education. Addressing both adverse selection and moral hazard is therefore essential for improving loan performance and achieving the ABP's objectives of agricultural productivity enhancement and sustainable financial inclusion (Stiglitz & Weiss, 1981; Mishkin, 2019).

2.3 Empirical Review

Recent empirical evidence demonstrates that non-performing loans (NPLs) in agricultural finance are determined by a multidimensional nexus of borrower characteristics, programme design, macroeconomic conditions, institutional quality, and exogenous production risks. Repayment performance is rarely attributable to a single determinant; rather, structural, behavioral, and contextual variables interact to shape loan outcomes.

Empirical studies on Nigeria's Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABP) largely document its positive impact on productivity, income, and access to credit, though evidence on repayment performance remains comparatively limited. Studies conducted in Benue, Kebbi, Ogun, Kano, Anambra, Niger, and Katsina States report improvements in rice yields, farm income, welfare, and access to subsidized inputs (Emokpae & Okoruwa, 2024; Gwadabe et al., 2024; Kolawole, 2025; Mufutau et al., 2025; Belewu, 2023; Attamah et al., 2025). However, constraints such as delayed loan disbursement, high interest rates, and yield losses were identified as major repayment challenges (Abdullahi et al., 2023; Muhammad et al., 2024; Sanusi et al., 2024; Ejiogu, 2021). In North-East Nigeria, insecurity and displacement significantly weakened repayment capacity. Although welfare gains are widely reported (Emokpae et al., 2024; Mufutau et al., 2025), repayment sustainability remains problematic. Evidence focusing specifically on repayment determinants shows that factors like income levels and livelihood outcomes positively influence repayment performance, whereas loan diversion and poor market prices increase default risk (Evbuomwan & Okoye, 2017; Andohol et al., 2020; Sanusi et al., 2024; Rotimi et al., 2024; Kassegn & Endris, 2022). These findings underscore structural vulnerabilities within agricultural credit schemes despite documented welfare improvements (Owusu et al., 2024; Balana & Oyeyemi, 2022).

From an overall agricultural lending perspective, borrower characteristics are consistently associated with NPL incidence. Education, farming experience, financial management skills, and borrower integrity significantly influence the creditworthiness of farmers in various

agricultural schemes (Ajah et al., 2014; Kaine & Ume, 2023; Kassegn & Endris, 2022; Kiros & Meshesha, 2022). Older farmers and those under constant supervision tend to exhibit higher repayment rates (Ajah et al., 2014; Rotimi et al., 2024). Household dependency burdens, however, intensify financial pressure and weaken repayment performance (Balana & Oyeyemi, 2022). Cultural perceptions of government-backed programmes and delays in loan disbursement further shape repayment behaviour (Abdullahi et al., 2023; Baraya et al., 2023). Recent evidence also highlights the role of income levels, crop yields, food security, and technology adoption in explaining repayment outcomes under ABP (Emokpae et al., 2024; Owusu et al., 2024; Gyong et al., 2022).

Also, programme design and institutional quality exert substantial influence on loan repayment outcomes of agricultural credit schemes and programmes. Weak credit appraisal systems, inadequate monitoring, and structural deficiencies in programme implementation are strongly associated with high default rates (Abel et al., 2025; Koye et al., 2024; Tomomewo et al., 2023; Ijuwo, 2024). The absence of moratoria during drought periods increases farmer vulnerability (Miriti et al., 2024; Balana et al., 2022), while untimely loan disbursement adversely affects repayment performance (Mohammed & Dumayiri, 2019; Baraya et al., 2023; Ejiogu, 2021). Corruption, political interference, and weak supervision further undermine repayment discipline (Salifu, 2025; Rotimi et al., 2024). Bureaucratic inefficiencies and administrative delays also elevate transaction costs and reduce net farm income, thereby weakening repayment capacity (Owusu et al., 2024). Comparative evidence demonstrates that group lending and peer monitoring reduce information asymmetries and enhance repayment outcomes (Salifu, 2025; Gyong et al., 2022), while both supply and demand-side credit constraints influence repayment performance (Muntaka et al., 2024; Balana & Oyeyemi, 2022; Kassegn & Endris, 2022).

Agricultural production risks remain central determinants of repayment performance of various agricultural credit schemes and programmes. Natural shocks such as floods and droughts disrupt farm productivity and undermine cash flows (Abraham & Fonta, 2018; Antonaci et al., 2014; Balana et al., 2022; Collier & Dercon, 2014). In Nigeria, floods, unsuitable seed supply, and delayed disbursement have been linked to repayment difficulties among ABP beneficiaries (Muhammad et al., 2024; Baraya et al., 2023; Ejiogu, 2021). Market volatility, agroclimatic extremes, and biological hazards significantly explain variations in default rates, while low commodity prices and weak market linkages constrain repayment (Owusu et al., 2024; Rotimi et al., 2024; Msomi, 2022). Climate disruptions also reduce lenders' willingness to extend credit to smallholders (Balana & Oyeyemi, 2022; Kassegn & Endris, 2022). Nonetheless, targeted government interventions during systemic shocks such as COVID-19 helped some farms maintain debt servicing capacity (Sanusi et al., 2024; Naili & Lahrichi, 2022).

Macroeconomic and institutional environments are equally decisive of these programmes. Exchange rate instability and rising input costs strain farmers' finances (Olasupo et al., 2014; Balana & Oyeyemi, 2022; Msomi, 2022), while high interest rates increase repayment hardships (Mejeha et al., 2019; Ejiogu, 2021; Naili & Lahrichi, 2022). Cross-country evidence identifies GDP growth, unemployment, inflation, and domestic savings as significant determinants of NPL levels (Kalimoldayev et al., 2025; Louzis et al., 2012; Msomi, 2022; Onyenekwe et al., 2025). Economic policy uncertainty, bank concentration, and weak institutional environments further exacerbate NPL ratios (Ozili, 2025; Ozili, 2019; Naili & Lahrichi, 2022; Okunade et al., 2022).

Institutional quality remains a robust explanatory factor that influences loan repayment outcomes. Weak regulatory frameworks and poor credit risk mitigation systems adversely affect loan repayment performance, whereas strong financial value-chain systems enhance sustainability (Tomomewo et al., 2023; Ijuwo, 2024; Naili & Lahrichi, 2022). Regulatory

quality and rule of law significantly explain cross-country variations in NPLs (Oni & Jonathan, 2023; Ozili, 2019; Msomi, 2022). Political instability and election-related uncertainty increase production and credit risks (Ozili, 2024; Naili & Lahrichi, 2022), while corruption and weak governance structures elevate default rates (Rotimi et al., 2024; Okunade et al., 2022). Infrastructure deficits, such as poor transport and inadequate storage facilities, raise production costs and limit market access, thereby constraining repayment capacity (Dorosh et al., 2010; Owusu et al., 2024; Balana & Oyeyemi, 2022).

2.4 Gaps in Literature and Need for the Study

The existing literature on non-performing loans (NPLs) in agricultural finance provides useful insights but remains fragmented and largely borrower-focused. Nigerian studies predominantly emphasize demographic and household characteristics, such as age, education, farming experience, and dependency ratios, as primary determinants of repayment (Ajah et al., 2014; Kaine, and Ume, 2023). However, comparative evidence indicates that borrower traits alone cannot sufficiently explain default patterns without effective programme design and strong institutional frameworks (Balana & Oyeyemi, 2022; Rotimi et al., 2024). This suggests an underrepresentation of structural and governance-related determinants in the Nigerian context.

Empirical research specific to the Anchor Borrowers' Programme remains limited and largely outcome-oriented, focusing on productivity, income, farmers' technical efficiency, level of poverty and welfare effects (Mohammed et al. 2025; Mufutau et al., 2025; Belewu, 2023), with fewer studies addressing repayment performance directly (Abdullahi, et al 2023; Kolawole, 2025; Sanusi, et al, 2024). Even when repayment is examined, the analysis centres on borrower attributes and economic shocks, while institutional design and governance mechanisms, particularly the role of Development Finance Officers, receive minimal attention.

These gaps necessitate a more integrated framework that simultaneously examines beneficiary-related, programme-specific, production, socio-economic, and institutional governance factors. Such an approach would provide stronger empirical grounding for policy interventions aimed at improving loan recovery under the ABP.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed survey research design to investigate the factors that led to non-performing loans in the Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABP) of CBN in Nigeria. The choice of a survey design is justified because it allows for the systematic collection of quantifiable data from a large group of respondents, thereby facilitating statistical analysis and enhancing the generalizability of the findings. Furthermore, it is suitable for understanding the experiences of the development finance officers (DFOs) who directly monitor and implement the programme in Nigeria's six geo-political regions.

3.1 Population and Sampling Technique

The study targets Development Finance Officers (DFOs) of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) who are responsible for implementing and monitoring the programme. A purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure that only respondents who had adequate and relevant professional knowledge concerning the programme being implemented were selected. This approach is justified because specialised knowledge of the programme, is unlikely to be evenly distributed across the population. Therefore, a total of 162 DFOs were identified as the survey

sample, cutting across the six geo-political zones of Nigeria. This number was considered sufficient to ensure regional representation and ensure easy data collection and analysis.

3.2 Sources and Data Collection Method

A structured questionnaire was applied as a tool for data collection. The questionnaire aimed to obtain quantitative data on the key aspects of the study, such as borrower characteristics and factors of ABP loan default. The questionnaire employed closed-ended Likert scale questions and multiple-choice items to ensure consistency, reliability and ease of statistical analysis. Questionnaires were sent electronically and physically to the Development Finance Officers (DFOs) through their social media, personal emails and internal communication system for absolute confidentiality so as to obtain objective responses.

3.3 Reliability and Validity

The study tool was formulated using consistent scales and surveys employed in prior research on factors that affect loan defaults. Content (face) validity was determined by the experts and reliability established using Cronbach’s alpha method of internal consistency. The Cronbach’s alpha values of the subscales (see Table 1) showed that the instrument is reliable. To further ensure reliability, the questionnaire was pre-tested on a small sample of DFOs (outside the study sample) and necessary adjustments made to enhance clarity.

Table 1

Cronbach Alpha Table

Item	Cronbach's Alpha
Beneficiary Related Factors (BRF)	0.806
Programme Specific Factors (PSF)	0.868
Agricultural Related Factors (ARF)	0.871
Socio-Economic Factors (SEF)	0.882
Institutional Environment Factors (IEF)	0.862
Non-Performing Loans in ABP (NPL)	0.855

Researchers’ Compilation (2025)

3.4 Model Specification

The model developed by Osunkoya et al., (2016) was adapted and refined to align with the specific objectives of this study. While the original model focused on macroeconomic and bank-specific determinants of non-performing loans (NPLs), this study extends the framework by incorporating additional determinants, including agricultural related factors, socio-economic factors, and institutional environment factors. The revised model is formulated using SEM notation as follows:

$$NPL_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BRF_i + \beta_2 PSF_i + \beta_3 ARF_i + \beta_4 SEF_i + \beta_5 IEF_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Where:

- NPLs is the latent variable for Non-Performing Loans (Dependent Variable)
- BRF_i , PSF_i , ARF_i , SEF_i and IEF_i represent the latent variables for beneficiary related factors, programme-specific factors, agricultural-related factors, socio-economic factors, and institutional environment factors, respectively (Independent Variables)
- $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ are the path coefficients representing the direct effects of each factor on NPLs.

- ϵ is the error term .

Note that each latent variable (BRF, PSF, ARF, SEF, IEF, NPLs) were measured by a set of indicators (observed variables).

3. 5 Model Estimation Techniques

The data collected was analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics was utilized to summarize the key characteristics of the sample and to identify factors contributing to non-performing loans. Inferential statistics of structural equation modeling was employed to examine the relationship between the independent variables (borrower characteristics, macroeconomic factors, environmental risks, and institutional influences) and the dependent variable of non-performing loans. Thus, the use of SEM in this study is justified by its ability to capture complex relationships, model latent variables, evaluate model fit, and handle simultaneous equations and importantly, SEM demonstrates robustness in handling data that deviate from strict normality assumptions, making it an appropriate choice for examining the multifaceted nature of factors contributing to non-performing loans in the ABP (Hair et al., 2019; Kline, 2016). SEM is particularly useful in exploring indirect and direct relationships between variables, which is essential when dealing with complex, interrelated factors such as borrower characteristics, macroeconomic factors, and institutional influences (Schumacker & Lomax, 2016). Furthermore, the method's flexibility in handling latent constructs and measurement errors such as normality issues, ensures that the study's findings is robust and meaningful (Byrne, 2016).

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section presents a comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the data collected through the survey.

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

Figure 1 presents the descriptive analysis which reveals that the majority of respondents have substantial work experience, with 28.8% having 11-20 years of experience and another 28.8% possessing 1-5 years of experience, followed by 23.2% with 6-10 years. A smaller proportion, 10.4%, has over 21 years of experience, while 8.8% reported having no experience. Regarding education, the workforce is highly educated, with 59.2% holding a Master's degree or MBA, and 40.8% possessing a Bachelor's degree or Higher National Diploma (HND). In terms of age, 49.6% of respondents fall within the 36-45 age range, indicating a predominance of middle-aged professionals in their peak career years, while 26.4% are aged 26-35, and smaller proportions are represented by those aged 46-55 (16.8%), 18-25 (4.8%), and above 56 (2.4%). The distribution of work positions highlights that Loan Officers (20.8%) and Recoveries Managers (19.2%) make up the largest segments, followed by Relationship Officers (15.2%), Programme Managers (6.4%), and Credit Managers (4.8%), with 33.6% categorized under other roles. These findings suggest that the workforce is both experienced and highly educated, dominated by middle-aged professionals in diverse roles, providing a solid basis for informed and practical insights into the subject of study.

Figure 1: Descriptive Analysis of Respondents

Source: Authors' Computation, (2025)

4.2 Descriptive Statistics of Identified Factors

Table 2 provides a descriptive analysis of the factors identified as contributing to the issue of Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) in Nigeria's Anchor Borrowers Programme. Among Beneficiary-Related Factors (BRF), "Willful or Intentional Default" (Mean = 4.52, SD = 0.74) and "Loan Diversion" (Mean = 4.36, SD = 0.727) were identified as the most significant issues, demonstrating a high level of agreement among respondents. On the contrary, demographic factors such as "Age" (Mean = 2.32, SD = 1.207) and "Gender" (Mean = 2.04, SD = 1.13) had relatively lower means, suggesting limited impact. Programme Specific factors (PSF) like "Poor Credit Risk Assessment" (Mean = 4.29, SD = 0.824) and "Non-Adherence to ABP Policy" (Mean = 4.23, SD = 0.942) were highly rated, indicating critical programme inefficiencies. However, variables such as "Strict Loan Tenor" (Mean = 2.22, SD = 1.282) and "Distance to ABP Financial Institution" (Mean = 2.28, SD = 1.282) had lower means, showing comparatively lesser significance.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Identified Factors

Category	Variable	Mean	SD	Variance
Beneficiary Related Factors (BRF)	Loan Diversion (BRF ₁)	4.36	0.727	0.529
	Willful or Intentional Default (BRF ₂)	4.52	0.74	0.547
	Lack of Integrity (BRF ₃)	4.28	0.765	0.585
	Age (BRF ₄)	2.32	1.207	1.456
	Gender (BRF ₅)	2.04	1.13	1.277
	Low Business Experience (BRF ₆)	3.13	1.175	1.38
	Low Household Income (BRF ₇)	2.83	1.212	1.469
	Low Educational Level (BRF ₈)	2.59	1.155	1.333
Programme Specific Factors (PSF)	Poor Credit Risk Assessment (PSF ₁)	4.29	0.824	0.679
	Top Management Influence (PSF ₂)	3.59	1.217	1.48
	High Loan Price (PSF ₃)	2.52	1.481	2.194
	Non-Adherence to ABP Policy (PSF ₄)	4.23	0.942	0.887

Category	Variable	Mean	SD	Variance
Agricultural Related Factors (ARF)	Inadequate Funding (PSF ₅)	3.62	1.341	1.797
	Inadequate Loan Moratorium (PSF ₆)	2.51	1.268	1.607
	Strict Loan Tenor (PSF ₇)	2.22	1.282	1.643
	Distance to ABP Financial Institution (PSF ₈)	2.28	1.282	1.644
	Agricultural Production Risks (ARF ₁)	3.39	1.166	1.359
	Natural Disaster (ARF ₂)	3.54	1.065	1.135
	Low Agricultural Production (ARF ₃)	3.38	1.214	1.474
	Weak Agricultural Commodity Value Chain (ARF ₄)	3.33	1.291	1.667
Socio-Economic Factors (SEF)	Marketing Risk (Low Price) (ARF ₅)	2.84	1.244	1.548
	Poor Market Linkage (ARF ₆)	2.83	1.382	1.91
	Persistent Rise in Prices (SEF ₁)	3.12	1.356	1.839
	Exchange Rate Volatility (SEF ₂)	3.04	1.366	1.866
	Corruption Issues Within the Programme (SEF ₃)	4.36	0.766	0.587
	Beneficiaries' Cultural Orientation (SEF ₄)	3.62	1.189	1.415
Institutional Environment Factors (IEF)	Household Expenses (SEF ₅)	3.17	1.224	1.499
	Number of Beneficiaries' Dependents (SEF ₆)	2.94	1.305	1.702
	Government Policy Inconsistency (IEF ₁)	3.25	1.311	1.718
	Bureaucratic Bottlenecks (IEF ₂)	2.86	1.192	1.42
	Capacity Limitation of Supervisory Organ (IEF ₃)	2.9	1.274	1.622
	Weak Legal System (IEF ₄)	2.99	1.243	1.544
	Poor Infrastructure (IEF ₅)	3.52	1.267	1.606
Energy Crisis Within the Country (IEF ₆)	3.22	1.371	1.879	
Insecurity Problem (IEF ₇)	4.22	1.013	1.026	

Source: Authors' Computation (2025)

Also, from Table 2 Agricultural Related Factors (ARF), "Natural Disaster" (Mean = 3.54, SD = 1.065) and "Agricultural Production Risks" (Mean = 3.39, SD = 1.166) were prominent, reflecting respondents' concerns about environmental and production challenges. Socio-economic factors (SEF) such as "Corruption Issues within the Programme" (Mean = 4.36, SD = 0.766) and "Beneficiaries' Cultural Orientation" (Mean = 3.62, SD = 1.189) stood out as critical socio-economic hindrances, whereas "Exchange Rate Volatility" (Mean = 3.04, SD = 1.366) and "Number of Beneficiaries' Dependents" (Mean = 2.94, SD = 1.305) appeared less impactful. Finally, institutional environment factors (IEF) revealed significant challenges, with "Insecurity Problem" (Mean = 4.22, SD = 1.013) and "Poor Infrastructure" (Mean = 3.52, SD = 1.267) being the most critical, whereas "Bureaucratic Bottlenecks" (Mean = 2.86, SD = 1.192) and "Weak Legal System" (Mean = 2.99, SD = 1.243) were deemed less severe. These findings underline the multifaceted nature of the issue, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions across various dimensions.

4.3 Application of Structural Equation Model

This section presents the results of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis, which was conducted to investigate the relationships between the factors influencing Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) in the Anchor Borrowers Programme of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). These factors include Borrower-Related Factors (BRFs), Programme-Specific Factors (PSFs), Agricultural-Related Factors (ARFs), Socio-Economic Factors (SEFs), and Institutional Environment Factors (IEFs). This section was divided into two parts; measurement model and the structural model.

4.3.1 Measurement Model

From the perspective of the measurement model the quality of the constructs was meticulously assessed through a comprehensive evaluation. An initial review of factor loadings revealed that fourteen out of thirty-five items fell below the recommended threshold of 0.50 and were consequently excluded from further analysis. The remaining 21 items exhibited strong correlations with their respective constructs, thereby affirming their validity (Pett et al., 2003). The multicollinearity test was examined using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values, all of which were below the critical threshold of 5, indicating that multicollinearity was not an issue (Hair et al., 2016). Detailed results are presented in Appendices 1 to 2.

Reliability was confirmed through Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability, with both metrics exceeding the benchmark of 0.70, demonstrating the stability and consistency of the measurement instruments (Hair et al., 2011). Convergent validity was assessed using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), where most constructs achieved AVE values greater than 0.50, thereby supporting convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 3. Construct Reliability Analysis (Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability)

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
ARF	0.810	0.911	0.937	0.787
BRF	0.953	0.881	0.875	0.717
ENPL	0.821	0.931	0.898	0.746
IEF	0.901	0.812	0.917	0.787
PSF	0.829	0.807	0.785	0.886
SEF	0.802	0.821	0.835	0.629

Authors' Computation from SmartPLS, (2025)

Table 3 presents the results of the construct reliability and convergent validity assessment. The Cronbach's alpha values for all constructs range from 0.802 to 0.953, exceeding the minimum recommended threshold of 0.70, thereby indicating a high level of internal consistency among the measurement items (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994; Hair et al., 2011). Similarly, the Composite Reliability indices (rho_a) and (rho_c) for all constructs are above 0.70, further confirming the reliability and stability of the constructs within the measurement model (Hair et al., 2016; Henseler et al., 2009). Convergent validity is evidenced by the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values, all of which surpass the benchmark of 0.50. This indicates that each construct explains more than 50 percent of the variance in its respective indicators, thus demonstrating adequate convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Overall, the results in Table 3 confirm that the retained measurement items are reliable and that the constructs are well represented by their indicators.

Discriminant validity was evaluated using both the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) and the Fornell-Larcker criterion, with results confirming the distinctiveness of the constructs. These are presented in Table 4 and 5.

Table 4. Discriminant Validity Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	ARF	BRF	ENPL	IEF	PSF	SEF
ARF						
BRF	0.565					
ENPL	0.839	0.646				

IEF	0.396	0.553	0.841			
PSF	0.387	0.781	0.271	0.379		
SEF	0.282	0.178	0.162	0.280	0.182	

Authors' Computation from SmartPLS, (2025)

Table 4 reports the discriminant validity assessment using the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT). All HTMT values are below the conservative threshold of 0.85, as recommended by Henseler, Ringle, and Sarstedt (2015). This suggests that each construct is empirically distinct from the others and that issues of construct overlap or redundancy are minimal.

The relatively moderate HTMT values observed between certain constructs (e.g., ENPL and IEF) remain within acceptable limits and are theoretically justifiable, given the conceptual relatedness of the constructs within the study context. Consequently, the HTMT results provide strong evidence of discriminant validity across all latent variables in the model.

Table 5. Discriminant Validity- Fornell and Lacker Criterion

	ARF	BRF	ENPL	IEF	PSF	SEF
ARF	0.887					
BRF	0.587	0.666				
ENPL	0.633	0.611	0.864			
IEF	0.097	0.575	0.733	0.887		
PSF	0.330	0.522	0.165	0.319	0.697	
SEF	0.227	0.111	0.095	0.224	0.077	0.793

Authors' Computation from SmartPLS, (2025)

Table 5 further evaluates discriminant validity using the Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion. As shown, the square roots of the AVE values (presented along the diagonal) for each construct are greater than the corresponding inter-construct correlations in the respective rows and columns. This confirms that each construct shares more variance with its own indicators than with other constructs in the model. The results thus reinforce the findings from the HTMT analysis and collectively demonstrate that discriminant validity is satisfactorily established. This indicates that the constructs capture unique theoretical concepts and are not unduly influenced by other latent variables in the model (Hair et al., 2016).

4.3.2 Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Analysis

From Table 6 and Figure 2 the structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis highlights the critical factors responsible for non-performing loans (NPLs) in the Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABP) in Nigeria, focusing on specific factors within each construct.

Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling showing the Factors Responsible for NPLs in the Anchor Borrowers’ Programme in Nigeria.

Figure 2: Factors Responsible for NPLs in ABP in Nigeria

Table 6: Factors Responsible for NPLs in the Anchor Borrowers’ Programme in Nigeria (structural model)

Constructs	Path Co-efficient	T statistics	P values
Beneficiary-Related Factors (BRF)-> ABP Non-Performing Loans (NPLs)	0.413	7.238	0.000
Programme-Specific Factors (PSF)> ABP Non-Performing Loans(NPLs)	0.113	2.939	0.003
Agricultural-Related Factors (ARF)> ABP Non-Performing Loans(NPLs)	0.199	3.612	0.000
Socio-Economic Factors (SEF)> ABP Non-Performing Loans(NPLs)	0.309	5.472	0.000
Institutional Environment Factors (IEF) > ABP Non-Performing Loans(NPLs)	0.215	5.158	0.000
Model Diagnostics			
R-square	R-square adjusted	Model_ Fit Summary	
0.854	0.847	SRMR	0.034
		NFI	0.652
		Q ²	0.753

Source: Researchers’ Computation, From SmartPLS, (2025)

From Table 6, the Beneficiary-related factors (BRF) showed the strongest influence on NPLs (Path coefficient = 0.413, T-statistics = 7.238, p < 0.001). Key issues driving this relationship include loan diversion (BRF1), willful or intentional default (BRF2), and lack of integrity (BRF3), highlighting the significant role of borrower behavior and ethical challenges in loan performance.

Programme-specific factors (PSF) also demonstrated a positive and significant impact on NPLs (Path coefficient = 0.113, T-statistics = 2.939, p = 0.003), with critical contributors being poor credit risk assessment (PSF1), top management influence (PSF2), and non-adherence to ABP policy (PSF4). These findings emphasize the need for improved governance and adherence to programme guidelines to mitigate repayment risks. Agricultural-related factors (ARF) were another significant determinant (Path coefficient = 0.199, T-statistics = 3.612, p < 0.001).

Factors such as agricultural production risks (ARF1), natural disasters (ARF2), low agricultural production (ARF3), and a weak agricultural commodity value chain (ARF4) highlight the vulnerabilities of the agricultural sector and its cascading effects on loan performance.

Socio-economic factors (SEF) had a substantial positive influence on NPLs (Path coefficient = 0.309, T-statistics = 5.472, $p < 0.001$). Key contributors include corruption issues within the programme (SEF3), beneficiaries' cultural orientation (SEF4), and household expenses (SEF5), which reflect broader socio-economic challenges impacting loan repayment. Institutional environment factors (IEF) also significantly contributed to NPLs (Path coefficient = 0.215, T-statistics = 5.158, $p < 0.001$). Government policy inconsistency (IEF1), poor infrastructure (IEF5), and insecurity problems (IEF7) emerged as critical factors, highlighting systemic challenges within the institutional environment that hinder effective loan performance.

Also, Table 6 presents the structural model overall performance with an R-squared value of 0.854. This indicates that approximately 85.4% of the variance in ABP Non-Performing Loans is explained by the predictors. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.847 accounts for the number of predictors and continues to reflect a strong model fit. Model diagnostics further confirm the robustness of the fit. The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) is 0.034, well below the acceptable threshold of 0.08, indicating excellent fit quality. Additionally, the Normed Fit Index (NFI) is reported at 0.652, suggesting a moderate overall fit. Importantly, the model demonstrates strong predictive relevance, as evidenced by the Stone–Geisser Q^2 value of 0.753. Since the Q^2 value is substantially greater than zero, it confirms that the model has high out-of-sample predictive accuracy for ABP NPLs, indicating that the exogenous constructs possess substantial predictive power beyond mere in-sample explanation (Hair et al., 2019).

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The SEM results identified loan diversion, intentional default, and lack of integrity as the most critical beneficiary-related factors (BRFs), demonstrating the strongest and most significant impact on non-performing loans (NPLs). These factors reflect moral hazard, where borrowers engage in opportunistic behaviour after disbursement (Agada et al., 2018). Households with higher dependency ratios also face financial pressures that weaken repayment capacity (Kaine, and Ume, 2023). This study confirms that opportunistic borrower behaviour remains a primary determinant of default even within structured government interventions like the Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABP), highlighting the need for stronger enforcement, rigorous borrower screening, and enhanced monitoring.

Programme-specific factors (PSFs), including poor credit risk assessment, top management influence, and non-adherence to ABP policies also strongly predict NPLs. Political interference and weak institutional processes have been shown to increase default risks in agricultural credit programs (Salifu, 2025; Abel et al., 2025; Koye et al., 2024). The study demonstrates that non-adherence to policies is nearly as influential as poor credit assessment, emphasizing that compliance and governance issues are central to NPLs in the ABP. Systemic agricultural risks, such as natural disasters, low production, and weak commodity value chains, further contribute to defaults. Floods, droughts, unsuitable seeds, and delayed loan disbursements have disrupted farm productivity and repayment capacity (Abraham & Fonta, 2018; Antonaci et al., 2014; Sanusi, 2024). Linking these risks to information asymmetry models, the study shows how systemic factors affect output and lender assessment, increasing default likelihood.

Socio-economic factors (SEFs), including corruption, negative perceptions of government credit schemes, and the use of loans for household expenses, also significantly influence NPLs. Many beneficiaries perceive government loans as a “national cake” to be exploited (Ajah et al., 2013; Abdullahi et al., 2023). Household pressures from high inflation further exacerbate loan diversion and repayment difficulties (Olasupo et al., 2014; Ozili, 2025). These findings reposition socio-economic factors as measurable predictors with effect sizes comparable to agronomic risks. Institutional environment factors (IEFs), such as policy inconsistency, inadequate infrastructure, and insecurity, emerged as significant determinants of NPLs. Insecurity reduces farm output and repayment capacity (Oni and Jonathan, 2023), while policy instability and poor infrastructure hinder programme effectiveness (Owoeye, 2025; Khan et al., 2024). The study highlights the interaction of institutional factors with information asymmetry, showing how governance, infrastructure, and security collectively influence repayment outcomes.

Theoretically, the study extends Information Asymmetry Theory by demonstrating that asymmetries affect multiple levels: borrower behaviour (loan diversion, integrity), institutional processes (risk assessment, policy adherence), and systemic socio-economic conditions (production risk, corruption, insecurity). This underscores that reducing NPLs in ABP requires integrated interventions across borrower conduct, institutional governance, and systemic risk management, rather than single-factor solutions.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study reveals that multiple interrelated factors contribute to the prevalence of non-performing loans (NPLs) in the Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABPs) in Nigeria, with significant implications for its sustainability. Beneficiary-related factors, such as loan diversion, willful default, and lack of integrity, highlight the pervasive role of moral hazard and the challenges of borrower accountability. Programme-specific factors, such as poor credit risk assessment and non-adherence to ABP policy, underscore institutional inefficiencies that weaken the programme's operational framework. Similarly, agricultural-related factors, including production risks, natural disasters, and weak value chains, reflect the vulnerability of the agricultural sector to systemic risks, while socio-economic and institutional factors further exacerbate loan defaults through corruption, policy inconsistency, poor infrastructure, and insecurity. The study concludes that, to enhance the performance of agricultural financing programmes like ABP in Nigeria there is the need to address the issues of information asymmetries, institutional weaknesses, and systemic risks. Based on these conclusions, it is recommended that:

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should ensure that robust screening processes that assess borrowers' integrity, financial capacity, and history of loan performance are regularly implemented. Proper monitoring of loan utilization should also be instituted, leveraging digital tools such as mobile-based loan monitoring applications to ensure compliance and mitigate moral hazard.

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should mitigate programme-specific inefficiencies by adopting advanced credit risk assessment models, such as machine learning techniques, to improve borrower profiling and risk categorization. Additionally, strict adherence to ABP policy guidelines should be enforced through regular audits and the establishment of an independent compliance oversight body.

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in collaboration with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security (FMAFS) in Nigeria should address agricultural-related risk factors by introducing innovative risk management strategies, into ABP mode of operations such as agricultural insurance schemes and climate-resilient farming practices. Also, by strengthening agricultural commodity value chains through public-private partnerships can also enhance market access and minimize production-related defaults.

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in collaboration with the Anti-Corruption Agencies in Nigeria can tackle corruption within the programme by prioritizing transparent governance practices, whistleblower mechanisms, and sanctions for offenders. Also, socio-economic pressures on borrowers, such as household expenses, can be alleviated by CBN integrating financial literacy training and community-based savings and credit groups into the programme.

The Federal Government of Nigeria, through its relevant ministries, should tackle institutional challenges such as policy inconsistency and inadequate infrastructure by formulating a stable and coherent agricultural financing policy. Additionally, strategic investments in rural infrastructure, including roads and irrigation systems, are essential to enhancing agricultural productivity and strengthening borrowers' capacity to repay loans.

5.1 Limitation of the Study

Despite its contributions, the study is not without limitations. Firstly, it relies on cross-sectional data, which constrains the ability to establish long-term causal relationships between identified factors and loan performance. Secondly, the issues such as self-reporting bias and lack of access to comprehensive loan-level datasets may have influenced the precision of some findings. Future studies track repayment behaviour and programme dynamics over time, offering more robust insights into causal effects. Also, comparative studies across different regions or agricultural credit programmes could provide broader perspectives on institutional and contextual influences on NPLs. Also, the perspective of other stakeholders such as the Anchors, the programme beneficiaries could compliment the position of the Development finance officers on the causes of NPLs in the ABP programme in Nigeria.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1. Factor Loadings							Appendix 2 Multicollinearity Test	
	ARF	BRF	ENPL	IEF	PSF	SEF		VIF
ARF1	0.668						ARF1	1.066
ARF2	0.726						ARF2	1.053
ARF3	0.838						ARF3	1.022
ARF4	0.770						ARF4	1.041
BRF1		0.641					BRF1	1.219
BRF2		0.752					BRF2	1.27
BRF3		0.856					BRF3	1.262
ENPL1			0.623				ENPL1	1.207
ENPL2			0.776				ENPL2	1.412
ENPL3			0.637				ENPL3	1.179
ENPL4			0.662				ENPL4	1.339
ENPL5			0.787				ENPL5	1.265
IEF1				0.864			IEF1	1.837
IEF5				0.796			IEF5	1.023
IEF7				0.835			IEF7	1.819
PSF1					0.741		PSF1	1.108
PSF2					0.781		PSF2	1.07
PSF4					0.713		PSF4	1.06
SEF3						0.670	SEF3	1.058
SEF4						0.758	SEF4	1.109
SEF5						0.697	SEF5	1.065

Authors' Computation from SmartPLS (2025)

Authors' Computation from SmartPLS (2025)